

Security, Privacy, and Resilience Controls for the 6G End-to-End System Developed in Hexa-X-II

Pawani Porambage¹, Noelia Pérez Palma², Diego Lopez³, Antonio Pastor³, Bin Han⁴, Betül Güvenç Paltun⁵, Ferhat Karakoç⁵, Prajnamaya Dass⁶, Stefan Köpsell⁶, Sonika Ujjwal⁷, Philipp Schulz⁸, Anton Schösser⁸, Pol Alemany⁹, Raúl Muñoz⁹, Ricard Vilalta⁹, José María Jorquera Valero², Manuel Gil Pérez², Antonio Skarmeta², Dinaj Attanayake¹, Amitha Mayya⁶, Ali Khandan Boroujeni⁶, Hans D. Schotten⁴, Sylvaine Kerboeuf¹⁰, Gerhard Fettweis^{6,8}, Mikko A. Uusitalo¹¹

¹VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, ²University of Murcia, ³Telefónica Innovación Digital, ⁴RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau, ⁵Ericsson Research Türkiye, ⁶Barkhausen Institut Germany, ⁷Oy LM Ericsson Ab, ⁸Technische Universität Dresden, ⁹Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), ¹⁰Nokia Bell Labs France, ¹¹Nokia Bell Labs Finland.

Abstract— The sixth generation (6G) of mobile networks is being developed to overcome limitations in previous generations and meet emerging user demands. As spearhead of the European research and development effort on 6G, the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) 6G Flagship project Hexa-X-II has a leading role for developing the technologies and anchoring 6G end-to-end (E2E) system. This paper summarizes the security, privacy, and resilience (SPR) controls identified by the Hexa-X-II project and their validation activities. Moreover, we share the SPR view on the 6G E2E system with the SPR features which are necessary to ensure the trustworthiness of 6G.

I. INTRODUCTION

The sixth generation (6G) of mobile networks is evolving to meet the unprecedented user requirements that the fifth generation (5G) could not fulfill. Many research efforts on 6G are being already undertaken by industry and academia, while standardization organizations have also initiated programs focused on 6G. In this context, the Hexa-X-II project is significantly contributing to making the 6G vision a reality. Unveiling the design guidelines for the 6G end-to-end (E2E) system, Hexa-X-II already presented a comprehensive methodology and a blueprint in [1]. This includes the infrastructure layer, network function layer, application enablement platform layer, and application layer, all complemented by a set of pervasive functionalities and various forms of connectivity. According to the general view of the 6G E2E system proposed by Hexa-X-II, security, privacy, and resilience (SPR) are collectively considered as pervasive functionality that affects all layers and the other pervasive functionalities.

To cater this, the project brings out the unique identification of relevant technological enablers particularly in the fields of SPR. It is important to highlight that these enablers are introduced as SPR controls, as special kind of enablers deeply integrated with other system-wide enablers, and intended to address specific threats, providing mechanisms to detect them and to mitigate their impact on system performance while

keeping trustworthiness aspects as a key value. Trustworthiness covers a wide range of aspects. While initial work [2] on these aspects has focused on security as the basis and privacy on top of security, the additional aspects of trustworthiness include resilience, in support of the availability and dependability required for an essential infrastructure, together with the necessary compliance with ethical frameworks. This paper summarizes the SPR view on the 6G E2E system, the SPR controls investigated in Hexa-X-II and the possible evaluation platforms considered for their validation, where further details are presented in project deliverables [3-6].

II. SECURITY, PRIVACY, AND RESILIENCE IN 6G

This section outlines the view from the Hexa-X-II project related to the SPR aspects of 6G. This entails a brief overview on the 6G threat landscape, classification of SPR features, and the SPR view on the 6G E2E system blueprint.

A. Threat Landscape in 6G

In the Hexa-X-II project, we analyze the potential threat landscape in 6G networks, which may occur due to residual risks of legacy networks, the increased risks of advanced technologies, and the evolution of the cyber-attack ecosystem [3]. Firstly, the residual risks are identified with respect to the widespread use of softwarization, virtualization, and cloudification of wireless network management and their related insecure operational practices. For instance, the deployment of virtual network functions or resource federation in multi-tenant environments and non-dedicated cloud environments will create further security threats. Secondly, the increased risks are identified due to the expansion in dimension and complexity of the 6G networks intended to satisfy novel 6G use cases that have stringent security requirements. The extensive use of artificial intelligence (AI) / machine learning (ML) technologies has also created unprecedented challenges while increasing risks in 6G networks. Thirdly, the expansion and evolution of the cyber-attack surface may occur with the more sophisticated adversaries that perform

Figure 1: Classification of SPR features as presented in Hexa-X-II.

AI-based attack methods or the advancements of quantum computing that break the conventional public-key infrastructure (PKI).

B. Classification of SPR Controls

The SPR controls that are designed to tackle these threats are classified based on their features and mapping onto the 6G E2E system blueprint developed by the project Hexa-X-II [1], [6]. As summarized in Figure 1, the security features are associated with three categories:

- i) The Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA) triad is achieved by the cryptographic mechanisms and the integration of redundancy mechanisms relating to the evolution of quantum-safe cryptography and the use of cloud-native architectural choices.
- ii) An Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA) framework is relevant to secure accessibility and identity management for human and non-human identities.
- iii) Automation of security closed-loop operations, including dynamic monitoring, attack detection, decision-making, and remediation actions, leading to security orchestration and the enforcement of security policies and/or intents.

Privacy features entail the confidentiality of data transferring and storing, data minimization mechanisms and the explicit support for consent and transparency. It is significant to extend these principles to manage as a combination of human and pervasive non-human identities in the 6G ecosystem.

To achieve system-level resilience with respect to the security features, it is required to ensure seamless availability and supported by closed-loop automation for security management in 6G networks. It includes the use of what-if scenarios to assess resilience under different conditions by using simulation mechanisms and integration with synthetic environments to emulate network segments. This requires establishing common interfaces to these environments and enabling seamless, on-demand integration to achieve the use of Network Digital Twins (NDTs) following the as-a-service model.

C. SPR view on 6G E2E System Blueprint

Figure 2 depicts the 6G E2E system blueprint proposed by Hexa-X-II, highlighting the integration of SPR features as part of pervasive functionalities and the availability of the specific enablers proposed for supporting trustworthiness in 6G networks. Let us next describe how SPR controls, and the features are related with the different layers, as pervasive functionalities and/or specific enablers.

Infrastructure layer: This layer provides different resources from the network-cloud continuum dedicated to sensing, computing, and storage resources as well as the devices. Cloud and computer service providers need to protect their own infrastructure from attack and ensure the isolation of workloads by following techniques such as confidential computing to achieve CIA and AAA features. Device-level security addresses the resource-constrained and ultra-low-power environments, where the SPR controls should include energy-aware security protocols and integrated trust mechanisms. Trustworthy system-on-chip (SoC) architectures can be designed to prevent data leaks, ensure resilience against attacks, and provide robust foundations for tiny ML applications.

Network functions layer: This layer includes logical and physical network functions that cover radio access network (RAN), core network (CN), transport networks and data networks (DN) to facilitate communication and beyond communication services. Security and privacy features should be carefully considered in this layer considering multi-level security solutions. For instance, when a mobile network operator (MNO) relies on data networks deployed by other compute resource providers AAA features should be protected. The associated SPR controls in this layer collectively ensure the resilience, availability, confidentiality, and integrity of systems and data. They enhance data recovery mechanisms to maintain resilience against loss or corruption, ensure secure communication through ciphering and integrity protection, and provide robust mobility management to support seamless transitions and uninterrupted service. Physical layer security (PLS) mechanisms aim to secure RAN protocols to strengthen the system's resilience and support CIA and AAA features by establishing secure communication channels. In Hexa-X-II, multiple enablers on PLS are presented in terms of RAN anomaly detection, context-aware security, and physical layer deception. In addition to these, the security and privacy aspects related to novel Joint communication and sensing (JCAS) services provided by the network functions layer are also studied. Some examples include how to secure JCAS protocols, signaling, and procedures, and how to ensure the privacy of sensing data management.

Application enablement platform layer: This facilitates processing offload for applications (e.g., extended reality) by providing Compute as a Service (CaaS). For instance, the user equipment (UE) acts as a CaaS consumer, whereas the DN is managed by the compute control node (CCN), which is the CaaS provider. When the CCN manages

Figure 2: 6G E2E system blueprint proposed by Hexa-X-II [5], highlighting the SPR elements.

compute resources at the DN and interfaces with the 6G system, it is important to establish a secure communication path between the UE's application client and the DN that ensures CIA and AAA features as well as the data privacy properties such as data minimization and supporting consent and transparency.

Management and orchestration: As a pervasive functionality in the 6G E2E system blueprint, management and orchestration can contribute to advancing security management through closed-loop control and using AI for automating security actions. This approach enables efficient and secure multi-agent-based network management while incorporating dynamic security control loops in the 6G E2E system. By orchestrating security services seamlessly together with the closed loops, the system will allow the enforcement of remediation policies by automated actions and the application of SecDevOps (i.e., security development and operation) mechanisms.

AI framework: The integration of the AI/ML framework in the 6G E2E system blueprint is pivotal for ensuring intelligent, adaptive, and efficient operations in all the layers. Robust and trustworthy AI mechanisms should be integrated, accompanied by privacy-enhanced data management and mechanisms to ensure CIA and AAA properties across network functions and connectivity options. Security automation in edge computing environments and accountability for shared data in federated domains are crucial to maintaining data integrity, reliability, and system trust.

Data framework: The key functionalities performed by the data framework such as data collection, distribution, and storage are required to be privacy compliant. This

entails not only aligning with the privacy-compliant regulatory requirements but also fulfilling data minimization, supporting consent and transparency, and achieving confidentiality in data processing and storage.

Multistakeholder 6G ecosystem: In a multi-stakeholder 6G ecosystem that allows resource federation among multiple administrative domains, there is a possibility of the transmission of security issues when proper isolation is achieved between the domains. To ensure robust and secure service, it is essential to incorporate continuous monitoring and security assessment to ensure E2E security. This includes developing dynamic and adaptive security solutions for threat detection, mitigation, prediction, and response in a multi-stakeholder environment. To provide strong isolation between services over a multi-tenant/multi-operator infrastructure, potential solutions include incorporating cryptographically protected multi-level security enablers or using security policies together with identity and access management schemes. It is also important to ensure trust in such a multi-stakeholder environment where each entity is certain that another will perform the specific actions as expected. This is addressed by the trust assurance with Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) mechanisms, and the application of specific enablers such as level of trust assessment function (LoTAF), and Transparent Notary Service (TNS), as described below.

Service exposure and new 6G services: This allows to securely expose services and capabilities provided by the 6G platform. The service exposure framework should support a strong authentication and authorization framework for secure identity and access management.

With the zero-trust security models supported by 6G networks, it is important to maintain dynamic and continuous verification of service exposure. With the advancements in ciphering techniques from PKI towards a quantum-safe era, it will even necessitate encrypting API communication using quantum-safe cryptographic protocols.

In particular, a number of specific enablers are proposed as a specific class of beyond-communications functions labelled Trust and Evidence. These functions would include the LoTAF (as exemplified in Figure 2), helping network users in assessing the trustworthiness of network services, the TNS as the common reference for identity (AAA) and crypto (CIA) features, and the possibility of exercising on-demand resilience evaluations.

III. SPR CONTROLS FROM HEXA-X-II

The Hexa-X-II project is involved in the identification and description of SPR controls that ensure the trustworthiness of the 6G E2E system. The SPR controls may provide different functionalities and address specific threats. They can be applied in 6G infrastructure and service design and planning as well as can be used by the 6G enablers with an SPR or any other objective. This section describes a selected set of SPR controls proposed in Hexa-X-II.

A. *Physical Layer Security (PLS)*

1) *Context-Aware Security*

Context awareness is used to enhance PLS. The channel measured between two legitimate devices during a time division duplex (TDD) communication within the channel coherence time is reciprocal in nature. This property is used in generating symmetrical encryption keys from the measured signals at the respective devices. The secret key generation (SKG) protocol involves randomness extraction, quantization, information reconciliation, and privacy amplification phases to generate the encryption keys. The achievable secret key rates depend on the parameters used during the different stages of the protocol and on the randomness present in the channel [4]. The randomness in the multipath channel depends on the channel context i.e., non-line of sight (NLOS)/line-of-sight (LOS), static, dynamic, mobility in the channel etc. Hence, knowing the context beforehand helps in increasing the achievable secret key rates by setting the optimal system parameters for the protocol. In this work, we use a classification algorithm to train the ML model to classify the channel frequency responses into LOS or NLOS static and dynamic channels. Among the tested models, Random Forest performed the best, and this is used to set the channel specific SKG parameters to implement the protocol and improve the SKG rates. This extracted randomness in the received signal power is converted into bits using quantization methods and the imperfections due to the channel noise and the receiver hardware can be corrected using distributed source coding techniques such as the Slepian-Wolf algorithm. The

privacy amplification deals with estimating the leakage in the information and the NIST randomness tests can be used to measure the quality of the secret keys produced during the successive channel measurements.

2) *Anomaly Detection for RAN*

The RAN architecture is evolving from a closed, unified infrastructure to an open, disaggregated, and softwarized system, offering flexibility and scalability. However, the distributed data processing and hierarchical formation in disaggregated architectures will cause difficulties for the direct integration of centralized security solutions (e.g., detection of security vulnerabilities) in such networks. Federated learning (FL) has a great potential in detecting anomalies in such disaggregated RAN environments for enhancing anomaly detection capabilities by allowing distributed model training across edge devices [4], [5]. This approach takes the advantage of the distributed nature of disaggregated RAN components, allowing for collaborative model training without the need for centralized data collection. The federated client models within disaggregated RAN nodes are trained using locally available data, and model vectors are communicated to the relevant first-level aggregators hosted in RAN intelligent controllers (RICs). Following aggregation, the calculated aggregator model vector is sent back to each local trainer in the same cluster, making the completion of a cluster round. After a predefined number of cluster rounds, first-level aggregators transmit their model vectors to the second-level aggregator located in a centralized RIC. Then, the global aggregator averages the received models and transmits the global model vector back to all federated clients, concluding one FL global round. The goal is to detect malicious UEs that are distributed across the network and to identify the slice type based on the performance indicators generated at the gNB per UE.

3) *Spectrum Anomaly Detection*

Considering the critical use cases anticipated for 6G – such as smart factories that connect cooperative robots – it may be necessary in certain scenarios to extend beyond RAN parameter monitoring and cover the wireless spectrum for maintaining a resilient network. In licensed bands, any interfering signal not transmitted by an authorized user is classified as a spectrum anomaly. Detecting such signals is essential, as they can compromise both communication performance and sensing accuracy. On the positive side, the functionalities and interfaces foreseen for 6G enable the extension of NDTs down to the physical layer, including the wireless channel. Information from environment sensing and localization can be bundled with information from resource allocation and combined with real-time ray tracing to generate an accurate estimation of the spectrum occupation, represented for example by a spectrogram. This NDT-based estimation can be compared against measurements obtained in the real world, where a deviation between the real world and the NDT indicates an anomaly. Implementing this security control allows for context-aware spectrum monitoring and enables a highly

precise anomaly detection, paving the way toward resilient 6G deployments for critical applications. A simulation-based evaluation has been executed in [5].

4) *Physical Layer Deception*

In addition, as an enhancement to PLS, which is classically a passive security measure, physical layer deception (PLD) is proposed to enable an active defense against potential eavesdroppers [4]. Combining PLS with cyber deception, it aims at causing loss to the interest of eavesdroppers, e.g., deceiving them with falsified information, or inducing them into self-exposure. The core idea is to replace randomly selected messages with falsified ones that are generated by ciphering the original messages with random keys. With every ciphered message, the key is multiplexed and sent together. With every message that is not selected for ciphering, a random litter sequence is multiplexed to keep the power profile undistinguishable from the ciphered ones. Appropriate resource allocation is then executed between the message part and the key/litter part in such a way, that the former is sufficiently exposed to all receivers, while latter is well perceivable by the legitimate user but protected from the eavesdroppers. This PLD framework can be understood as a semantic security approach and has been numerically demonstrated effective with both orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) and non-orthogonal multiplexing schemes [6].

B. *Trustworthy AI/ML*

Trustworthiness of AI/ML encompasses elements like the robustness of AI/ML against security attacks (e.g., poisoning attacks), privacy and data confidentiality, transparency, and explainability.

1) *Robust Federated Learning*

FL is expected to be important for collaborative ML in 6G. It can be crucial to consider both privacy and security together in FL. To address this requirement, FASIL (i.e., A challenge-based FrAmework for Secure and prIvacy-preserving federated Learning) framework was introduced [5-7]. The FASIL framework can be utilized independently across different components for various FL applications instead of deploying in the center of the E2E 6G system [7]. For example, UEs can function as clients, while a network element within RAN or core acts as the server, or network data analytics functions (NWDAFs) in different network slices as clients, with a single NWDAF serving as the server, or base stations functioning as clients linked to a core network function server. Similar setups can be established for the management layer and can support various AI/ML applications within the 6G E2E system while effectively addressing both privacy and security concerns.

2) *Robust Intrusion Detection Systems*

Intrusion detection systems (IDS) are crucial for monitoring network traffic and highlighting potential threats and responding to the evolving threats in real-time. When enhanced with ML, these systems can efficiently detect anomalous activities. However, ML vulnerabilities

exploitable by adversarial attacks not only threaten IDS control, but also sensitive data and critical network processes. An attacker exploiting these weaknesses could launch multiple attacks that would overcome existing defenses and ultimately break the defense mechanisms. For this reason, it is important to not only create advanced IDSs using ML but also to provide strong security measures in place. Solving this sophisticated problem requires a comprehensive framework that combines the strengths of ML against adversarial attacks, handling complex attack vectors, and real-time applicability. These measures might include regularly updating the systems and training them with a variety of data. In addition to current approaches, incorporating explainable AI (XAI) to detect malicious behaviors, is proven to be effective in the proposed adversarial detection framework [5].

C. *JCAS Security and Privacy*

The introduction of the JCAS poses several new security and privacy threats [3]. Some of the existing security controls available in 5G could be used for JCAS-specific authentication, authorization, and access control. However, considering the UE as a sensing unit, novel security controls are needed to authorize the sensing requests and before utilizing the UE resources for sensing activities. In order to protect the personally identifiable information involved in the sensing data, new controls like data anonymization and data minimization could be used. Other than applying these privacy controls to the collected sensing data, regulating the parameters sensing resolution and accuracy could avoid collecting sensitive data from restricted areas. Furthermore, some new functions needed to impose consent and transparency requirements while adhering to the sensing policies [5]. A similar type of controls should also be designed for the UE and gNB involved in sensing data processing.

D. *Level of Trust Assessment Function (LoTAF)*

Hexa-X-II presents a LoTAF to guarantee security aspects for cloud continuum scenarios. LoTAF is a neutral, bidirectional, and intelligent service supporting trustors (users) in making informed decisions and provisioning trustees (network providers) insights into service compliance regarding 6G security requirements. Hence, LoTAF streamlines the trustworthiness assessment of network services before and after they are instantiated, adhering to well-known standards (e.g., ITU-T Y.3057 and service assurance for intent-based networking (IBN) architecture). Concerning the LoTAF functionalities, the key activities are split into two main phases: i) semantic understanding, mapping, and information representation to handle knowledge graphs and agreements in terms of trust between parties; and ii) monitoring of service assurance to check deviations on agreed trust requirements and apply rewards or punishments on an initial LoT. All in all, LoTAF paves the way to enhance security and trustworthiness of 6G network services endowing users and providers with valuable insights and decision-making support [5], [6].

E. Quantum resistive cryptography

The integration of post-quantum cryptography (PQC) primitives into existing software frameworks is advancing, with the library implementation, helping to harmonize PQC with established security protocols such as transport layer security (TLS) protocol. As the first mobile network architecture designed with these new cryptographic considerations in mind, the 6G network should not only integrate PQC but also evaluate the consequences of the cryptographic shift on network structure, operations, and efficiency. The transition to quantum-resistant cryptography is also exploring the synergy between PQC and quantum key distribution (QKD), aiming to support adaptive key distribution, necessary for the varied operational demands of telecommunications infrastructure for long transition periods. The experiments in Hexa-X-II are focused on the impact of current practices for protocol security, especially in terms of availability and performance [5].

F. Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs)

DLTs provide a robust alternative to avoid the need of third parties to monitor requests from clients to providers by enabling decentralized management and immutable recording of network configurations, enhancing security against tampering and unauthorized changes. To this end, Hexa-X-II investigates the use of DLT [1] with a private, permissioned ledger where topology changes are recorded as transactions ensuring that only those authorized stakeholders are able to make changes [4]. With that, securely storing and sharing network topology information for network management decisions contributes to achieving a trustworthy multi-stakeholder scenario.

IV. EVALUATION PLATFORMS

As persistent security and privacy are paramount in the design of the 6G E2E system, Hexa-X-II considers the integration of comprehensive security frameworks, including quantum-resistant cryptography, trustworthy AI, and confidential network deployment, ensuring a secure and trustworthy environment for 6G services [5].

For example, SecDevOps mechanisms in Hexa-X-II systematically quantify service privacy levels using a declarative, service-specific privacy manifest. This manifest, detailing privacy service definitions, is analyzed with predefined metrics and algorithms. The privacy score, derived from both developer-provided and automatically assessed information, comprehensively evaluates data processing, storage, and communication. The architecture supports continuous privacy monitoring and updates, promoting ongoing refinement of privacy practices through DevPrivOps. Moreover, the architecture enhances privacy and trust by integrating several key components. The management API uses threat risk assessor (TRA) output for privacy quantification, while the zero-trust security and identity management component performs continuous trust evaluation of

network functions and entities. AI algorithms assist in trust evaluation and provide proactive notifications about trustworthiness. The security orchestrator employs AI to manage function chaining and orchestration, ensuring quality, performance, and security across network segments and domains. This orchestrator considers various network parameters and collaborates with other managers to implement countermeasures, thereby ensuring the resilience and reliability of 6G network services. Additionally, the work emphasizes practical outcomes, such as the DevSecOps pipeline and the use of what-if scenarios in an NDT to evaluate the impact of different measures. The interested readers can refer [5] and [6] to check the outcome results of the evaluation platforms.

V. CONCLUSION

As summarized in the paper, SPR related work in the Hexa-X-II project was started with the identification of threats and enhancing the opportunities for detection and mitigation known as the 6G security delta. The integration of advanced enablers in the 6G ecosystem requires rigorous SPR measures to ensure trustworthiness of the 6G E2E system, as enablers both support and depend on the SPR controls. As future work, the SPR view presented in Hexa-X-II aims to integrate the given results and other relevant SPR enablers from SNS projects.

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